

ANALYSIS OF OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY MARKET DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The article considers current trends in the development of the global renewable energy market. The features and problems of using renewable energy sources are studied. Based on the generalized experience and practice of stimulating the production and use of renewable energy sources, the possible directions of state influence on the formation of the domestic market for alternative energy sources are determined.*

Keywords: *renewable energy sources, alternative sources, «green energy», energy efficiency, alternative sources of energy, power industry.*

In recent years, there has been an active development of alternative energy sources. The leaders in this area are the countries of Europe and the USA, Germany, China, Japan.

With record-breaking growth in the share of renewables in its energy mix, Germany has continued to lead the EU in terms of CO₂ emissions for many years. The Germans, successively closing nuclear power plants, began to increase coal imports from Russia to make up for the missing power. A paradoxical situation emerged: in an effort to “green” its energy as much as possible, Germany, on the contrary, increased its “dirty” coal generation.

Even in Denmark, which plans to switch completely to renewable energy by 2050, the debate continues about the long-term cost-effectiveness of renewable energy sources. And you can understand the skeptics. Recently, there are too many high-profile examples of projects that have not been implemented that are related to renewable energy.

For example, "solar giant" SunEdison (USA) was the largest company in the field of solar energy with a capitalization of ten billion dollars, but failed to cope with debt obligations and was forced to declare bankruptcy. Another US company, Aquion Energy, which developed batteries for green energy storage, is now being sold off piecemeal and has had to cut nearly all of its R&D staff.

The history of the development of energy (as a physical quantity) is reflected in a number of works [9; 10], etc.). Researchers note that back in 1686, G. W. Leibniz was close to what corresponds to modern ideas about mechanical energy, although he did not use this term. In 1807, the English scientist Thomas Young, one of the founders of the wave theory of light, introduced it into scientific use, thereby giving this concept a scientific status [9]. The concept of kinetic energy was first used by the British physicist and mechanic W Thomson [10].

In 1847, at a meeting of the Physical Society in Berlin, G. Helmholtz first introduced the term potential energy into mechanics, understanding it as the energy of stressed forces, and also described and mathematically substantiated the law of conservation of force (energy). According to other authors [10], the concept of potential energy was first used in 1853 by a Scottish engineer, mechanic and physicist, one of the founders of technical thermodynamics, W. Rankin. Nobel Prize winner R. Feynman, noting the various forms of existence of energy, writes: “There is energy associated with motion (kinetic energy); the energy associated with the gravitational interaction (it is called the potential energy of

gravity); thermal, electrical and light energy; elastic energy in springs; chemical energy and, finally, the energy that a particle possesses by virtue of its existence alone - this energy directly depends on the mass” [12].

One of the main disadvantages of renewable energy sources is the dependence on external factors (the presence of solar radiation directly from the wind, and so on) and the instability of electricity generation. To compensate for the drops that arise, again, it is necessary at the expense of the base generation. Technologies that are associated with the accumulation and storage of energy from renewable energy sources can solve this fundamental problem. It is the creation of industrial storage devices that can accumulate very large amounts of energy that will make it possible to make the final and total transition to "green" energy.

Fig.1. Energy sources. [16]

Energy plays an extremely important role in ensuring the sustainable and safe development of society. From the point of view of the resource criterion, the sufficiency and reliability of providing electricity and heat to the growing needs of the economy and the population are of decisive importance; harmful substances into the environment.[14]

According to statistics, as a result of the efforts made in the EU countries, Canada, as well as in rapidly developing economies (Brazil, India, China), electricity generation from renewable sources amounts to tens of billion kWh, in the USA - more than a hundred billion kWh per year . In the EU countries, in which the share of these sources in the production and consumption of electricity in 2001 was less than 1%, as in Russia, in 2004 it reached 8.2%, and in 2010 - 12% [22, With. 12; 19, p. 12]. In the United States, the corresponding figures were about 2.2% in 2004 and 4.0% in 2010 [1].

The European Directive on renewable energy sources of June 2008 (EU Renewable Energy Directive) provides for an increase in this indicator by 2020 to 20% (in 2009 it was specified: 21% for the generation of electricity and 20% for thermal energy) . The new US legislation, adopted under President B. Obama, provides for an increase in this indicator to 10% in 2012 and up to 25% in 2020 [2]. It is estimated that the implementation of this law in the United States, in addition to environmental benefits, by 2030 will save consumers \$ 300 billion and create more than 400 thousand jobs.

The experience of Australia deserves attention, not least because of the similarity of its economy with the Russian one in terms of the significant contribution of the primary sector, primarily fuel and energy and minerals, to GDP production. In 2000, a law was passed there providing for the introduction of a mandatory norm for the use of renewable energy sources and bringing their share in total consumption to 10% by 2010. Since, due to the high rates of development (Tables 1-3), this indicator was achieved already in 2009, then a new law was adopted (an addendum to the law on renewable energy), obliging to increase this share, as in the EU, up to 20% by 2020 [3].

The data on China and India are indicative. In May 2009, the latter set the task of bringing the share of renewable energy sources to 10% by 2012, primarily through the accelerated development of solar energy, which turns this country into one of the world leaders in this field [4].

In China, its 2006 Renewable Energy Law requires large energy pools to generate 3% of electricity from renewable sources (excluding hydropower) by 2010 and 8% by 2020. According to the new program for the long-term development of the country's energy sector, the share of these sources in 2020 is set at 15%. In 2010, the energy intensity of China's GDP should have decreased (no data for 2010 yet) by 20% compared to 2005; in 2010-2015 (according to the XII five-year plan for the development of the country) - by another 20-23%, or 36% of the 2005 level [5] In 2020, in accordance with the intentions stated in the 2009 Copenhagen Accord, compared with the same base year, the reduction should be 40-45%; it was announced that by 2050 the energy intensity of GDP would decrease by 75-85% compared to 2010, or by 60-68% from the level of 2005 [5]. The real rate of decline in the energy intensity of GDP in China in 2006-2009. amounted to 3.5% in average annual terms, ensuring a 15% reduction in the energy intensity of GDP. If, in terms of the average annual rate of decline in the energy intensity of GDP, the normative threshold for Russia (3.3% in 2008-2020) is close to China's, then in terms of the share of renewable sources in the total volume of its production, Russia is more than four times inferior to China.

It is noteworthy that laws to support the development of alternative energy in China and India, as well as developed countries, were adopted during the global economic crisis and, despite the decline in production and investment, are yielding significant results. The development of this energy, including renewable energy, is considered there not only as an important direction for the transition to a new (sixth) technological order, for which the development of alternative energy is one of the most important distinguishing features, but also as a powerful anti-crisis tool, first of all, solving the problem of employment [5].

As for the energy sector itself, the development of alternative energy will continue to stimulate the diversification of sources of energy supply for the growth of the world economy. [15]

According to British Petroleum Corporation forecasts, in the next 20 years, non-fossil fuels may for the first time become a major factor in the growth of energy production: their contribution to the increase in production, which in 1990-2010. amounted to 17%, may increase to 36% in 2010-2030, including renewable sources - from 5 to 18%. At the same time, the total contribution of non-fossil energy sources (including the energy of water and the atom) to the growth of energy production for the first time in modern history can exceed the contribution of any single fossil energy source. At the same time, the total share of coal, oil and natural gas in the growth of energy production is likely to decrease from 83 to 64% [6].

In recent years, the G7 states and a number of other OECD energy-importing countries have increasingly raised the issue of eliminating these fossil fuel subsidies and using them instead to stimulate the development of alternative energy, including under the pretext of climate change mitigation. According to their calculations, this would contribute to the maximum possible (along with the countries of Eastern Europe that are not members of the EU) reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in Russia: in 2020 - by 17%, in 2050 - by 34% less than in the case if the mentioned subsidies were kept [7].

Noting the need for technological innovation, one cannot underestimate the importance of qualitative changes in the field of institutional innovation. A number of considerations regarding formal institutions, most notably the development of the regulatory framework, have been outlined above. Here we especially emphasize the important role of development in the sphere of informal institutions (traditions, stereotypes of behavior, etc.) and traditional experience and knowledge directly related to them.

We are talking about the need and opportunities for the rediscovery and practical use of the so-called traditional knowledge and culture - customs of behavior, skills, technologies, etc., which are characterized by resource conservation, including energy conservation, combined with adaptation to complex natural, first of all, climatic conditions. They have been accumulated for centuries by the local population, especially the indigenous peoples of Russia, as well as foreign countries: for example, in the construction of houses - the traditions and experience of using wood (logs), deer skins and snow, bamboo and teak. The huge and unique potential of this knowledge and technology is still poorly reflected or completely absent in modern standards. At the same time, its efficient use would significantly reduce the costs of transition to a new type of economy with a high share of alternative energy, primarily energy-saving and energy-efficient systems, as well as renewable sources.

To do this, it is necessary to solve a very complex double task: to ensure the maximum possible identification, thorough documentation and scientific expertise of this category of knowledge, which is impossible without the movement towards each other of their carriers - the local population and representatives of the scientific community. This, in turn, will require the first to overcome traditional isolation and alienation, and the second to move away from the perception of both traditional knowledge and culture as something insignificant, unworthy of the attention of "big" science and industry, and a sense of the superiority of modern specialists and the latest technologies. The world leaders in the field of power engineering as a whole are still the USA, Germany, Japan, France, Italy. Obviously, in the foreseeable future, Russia cannot compete with them on the global market,

nor can it completely replace foreign solutions and technologies with imports. The market has already been divided, and the main share in its structure in the coming years will continue to be occupied by the largest foreign companies.

Therefore, the main goal for today is the integration of all companies into global chains, cooperation with world leaders, technology transfer and further localization of the production of equipment that is not available in country, including for projects in the field of alternative energy.

The active development in recent years of the renewable energy sectors has made it possible to connect a large number of domestic machine-building, metalworking and electrical enterprises to the development of renewable energy. And every year the level of localization of key equipment for renewable energy will grow, thus forming new high-tech branches of the domestic industry.

Such a rigid approach to assessing knowledge, which a priori establishes its value, should give way to an approach based on assessing the effectiveness of the contribution of knowledge to the development of the economy, security and progress of society.

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